

Occupational and structural determinants of burnout among Spanish physiotherapists: a systematic review

María del Pilar Suja Garrido, MSc.

ABSTRACT:

Background: Burnout is a multidimensional occupational syndrome characterised by emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and reduced personal accomplishment. Although widely studied among physicians and nurses, evidence focusing on physiotherapists remains limited, particularly in the Spanish context.

Objective: To synthesise available evidence on burnout among Spanish physiotherapists and identify associated occupational and structural determinants.

Methods: A systematic review was conducted across PubMed, MEDLINE (Ovid), Web of Science, Scopus and Trip. After screening 4,131 records and applying predefined eligibility criteria and CASP methodological appraisal, seven cross-sectional studies were included.

Results: Moderate levels of emotional exhaustion and depersonalisation were consistently reported, with higher scores in nationwide samples. Workload variables, including number of patients per day and limited consultation time, were associated with increased burnout scores. Employment precarity, sector differences and income disparities emerged as relevant structural determinants. Early-career professionals appeared particularly vulnerable.

Conclusions: Burnout among Spanish physiotherapists appears strongly influenced by structural occupational conditions rather than solely individual factors. Addressing workload regulation, employment stability and organisational support may be essential for workforce sustainability and quality of care.

INTRODUCTION

Background

Christina Maslach and Susan E. Jackson introduced the burnout concept in the scientific literature as a syndrome characterised by emotional exhaustion (EE), depersonalisation (DP), and reduced personal accomplishment (PA). Since its first appearance, burnout definition has evolved, with one of its latest definitions being provided by the World Health Organisation (WHO) in the 11th International Classification of Diseases, which describes burnout as a syndrome resulting *from chronic workplace stress that has not been successfully managed* (1). Some researchers have also stressed the multidimensional energy depletion that burnout implies to the body, linking it with different illnesses such as metabolic, sleep and cardiac alterations, among others (2).

Beyond its clinical description, burnout has been theoretically conceptualised through occupational stress models that help explain its development. The Job Demands–Resources (JD–R) model proposes that burnout arises when high job demands (such as workload, emotional labour or time pressure) are not adequately balanced by job resources, including organisational support, autonomy and professional development opportunities (3). Complementarily, Conservation of Resources theory (4) conceptualises stress as a consequence of actual or threatened loss of valued resources, such as time, energy, social support or financial stability. Together, these frameworks situate burnout not merely as an individual psychological response but as a phenomenon embedded within structural and organisational conditions.

Burnout and workplace stress are key challenges in the healthcare sector, affecting both professional and patient outcomes. The nature of physiotherapy requires maintained physical activity, manual effort, and continuous interaction with patients, often under conditions of time pressure. Physical therapists (PTs) frequently manage high patient loads, administrative burdens, and demanding schedules, which can cumulatively contribute to occupational stress (5). From a JD–R perspective, these characteristics represent persistent job demands that may accelerate emotional exhaustion if not buffered by sufficient organisational resources.

Another significant contributor is the type of patients PTs work with. Treating individuals with chronic pain, degenerative conditions, or long-term rehabilitation needs often involves slow progress and limited short-term improvement. Over time, this gap between professional effort and visible patient outcomes can diminish motivation, deteriorate the therapeutic alliance, and intensify stress, further increasing the risk of EE and DP of the patient (6).

Burnout has been linked to both external factors (such as workload, organisational support, and job precarity) and personal factors (including coping style, personality traits, and resilience). These triggers interact over time, progressively increasing vulnerability to the syndrome. The development of burnout has even been conceptualised as a 12-stage process, often described as a gradual progression rather than a sudden event (7). As these stages advance, professionals may experience behavioural withdrawal, emotional strain and psychological deterioration that can ultimately require medical attention. This staged model reinforces the importance of early detection and intervention, particularly in professions characterised by sustained physical and emotional demands.

Generally, burnout syndrome (BOS) is characterised by exhaustion, job distancing, and reduced professional efficacy (1). However, in healthcare settings, job distancing often manifests as emotional withdrawal from patients rather than from tasks alone (6). This interpersonal aspect is especially critical in physiotherapy, where the therapeutic alliance is central to patient motivation, adherence, and recovery outcomes. Patient depersonalisation can erode empathy (8), gradually compromising the quality of therapeutic relationships (9) and diminishing the relational meaning that professionals typically derive from caregiving.

This process may generate a negative feedback loop for the professional: reduced empathy compromises therapeutic engagement, weakened therapeutic engagement diminishes perceived treatment impact, and this erosion of meaning further reduces PA. In turn, declining PA can intensify EE and reinforce DP, contributing to a deeper and more persistent state of burnout.

Within this cycle, burnout does not operate merely as an individual emotional state but as a relational and systemic process, particularly salient in professions such as physiotherapy that rely heavily on sustained interpersonal interaction.

The Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) (10) remains the most widely used instrument in burnout research, assessing the three core dimensions of EE, DP and PA across diverse cultural contexts. Nevertheless, as the construct has evolved, alternative instruments have been developed to capture additional nuances. The Bergen Burnout Inventory (11) incorporates cynicism towards the meaning of work; the Copenhagen Burnout Inventory (12) focuses specifically on exhaustion; and the Spanish Burnout Inventory (13) includes dimensions such as indolence and guilt, reflecting context-specific experiences. These alternative scales highlight that burnout is a multidimensional and context-dependent phenomenon, and the choice of instrument can influence how burnout is conceptualised and interpreted, particularly when examining associated variables. For this reason, several

studies complement the MBI with additional measures, such as the Socio-Occupational Stress Scale (SOSS/POSS), which contextualises burnout in relation to perceived occupational stressors (14), and the Interpersonal Reactivity Index (IRI), which assesses multidimensional empathy components (15).

Despite growing research on burnout among healthcare professionals, studies specifically addressing PTs in Spain remain limited. Only one systematic review published within the last decade has examined risk factors associated with PT burnout (16). That review identified certain non-modifiable factors, such as years of experience, age, gender and fewer years of employment. However, it also highlighted forty-nine modifiable psychological, environmental and sociodemographic contributors.

Burnout has significant negative consequences for PTs, affecting not only professional functioning but also their overall well-being. High levels of EE, DP, and reduced PA can diminish job satisfaction, increase psychological distress, and higher absenteeism and turnover rates, thereby exacerbating workforce shortages (17). These effects extend beyond professionals themselves: burnout has also been linked to reduced healthcare quality and compromised patient safety (18).

In this context, synthesising available evidence on burnout among Spanish physiotherapists is particularly relevant. Given the profession's physical demands, close patient interaction and evolving employment conditions, understanding the interplay between occupational demands, structural factors and personal resources is essential for informing sustainable workforce strategies and protecting both professional well-being and patient care quality.

METHODS

Design

A systematic review was conducted to synthesise evidence on burnout among practising physiotherapists in Spain. The review followed PRISMA 2020 guidelines, although no protocol was registered.

Search strategy

Electronic searches were performed in PubMed, MEDLINE (via Ovid), Web of Science, Scopus and Trip up to march 2025. A comprehensive search strategy was developed using free-text terms and controlled vocabulary (MeSH). The final Boolean search string was: (“workplace stress” OR “occupational stress” OR “burnout”) AND (“physical therapist” OR

“physiotherapist”) AND “Spain”. Reference lists of included studies were manually screened for additional relevant publications.

Eligibility criteria

Studies were included if they were focused on active Spanish physiotherapists and assessed burnout or occupational stress using validated instruments. They had to be peer-reviewed articles published in Spanish or English that employed quantitative or mixed methods designs (qualitative studies were not found).

Study selection and data extraction

After deduplication, 4,131 records were screened by a single reviewer. Full texts of potentially eligible studies were assessed for inclusion. The study selection process is described in Figure 1. Data were extracted on study design, sample size, participant demographics (sex, age, years of experience, region, sector, work shifts), work setting, instruments used, and burnout outcomes.

Quality assessment

Methodological quality was evaluated using the CASP checklist for cross-sectional studies. Only studies rated as moderate or high quality were included.

Data synthesis

Due to heterogeneity in sample sizes, regional representation, measurement instruments, and reported outcomes, formal meta-analysis was not feasible. A narrative synthesis was conducted, structured around core burnout dimensions (EE, DP, PA), sociodemographic and occupational determinants, and relational and cognitive variables.

Figure 1.

RESULTS

Study characteristics

Seven cross-sectional studies were included, with sample sizes ranging from 115 to 472 participants, with a total of approximately 2,217 professionals. The three published by Rodríguez-Nogueira (8,9,19) assess the entire Spanish territory, while the other four focus on five different autonomous communities: Andalusia (Cadiz) (20), Extremadura (6), Valencia and Murcia (21), and Madrid (22). Among the seven studies, both public and private settings were covered, as well as mixed employment arrangements. A summary of these can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Data extraction

Author	Year	Study type	Study design	Region	Setting	Sample size	Outcomes
Carmona-Barrientos et al.	2020	Observational	Cross-sectional	Cádiz	Public and private practice	272	MBI SOSS
González-Sánchez et al.	2016	Observational	Cross-sectional	Extremadura	Public and private practice	115	MBI-HSS SDLVQ
Gisbert et al.	2008	Observational	Cross-sectional	Murcia & Valencia	Public and private practice	261	MBI Workplace assessment questionnaire
Rodríguez-Nogueira et al.	2022	Observational	Cross-sectional	Spain	Public and private practice	472	MBI-HSS IRI
Rodríguez-Nogueira et al.	2024	Observational	Cross-sectional	Spain	Public and private practice	471	MBI-HSS WAI-S EBPQ-19
Rodríguez-Nogueira et al.	2021	Observational	Cross-sectional	Spain	Public and private practice	472	MBI-HSS EBPQ-19
Grande-Alonso et al.	2023	Observational	Cross-sectional	Madrid	Private sector	174	MBI-HSS

Participants were predominantly female (46–70%), with mean ages between 29 and 35 years, and professional experience ranging from 5 to >10 years. Most participants worked in

private practice, though some studies included both public and private sectors. Work shifts varied between continuous and split schedules, and patient loads differed significantly across settings.

Sociodemographic and professional characteristics are summarised in Table 2.

Burnout Assessment Instruments

All included studies used the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI or MBI-HSS) to assess EE, DP and PA. A summary of results can be seen in Table 3. Complementary instruments were employed in several studies to capture additional facets of occupational stress and relational functioning:

- SOSS/POSS was used in one study (14).
- IRI was employed to assess multidimensional empathy in one study (15).
- The Working Alliance Inventory-Short (WAI-S) assessed the quality of the therapeutic alliance in one study(9)
- The Evidence-Based Practice Questionnaire-19 (EBPQ-19) evaluated attitudes, knowledge, and practice related to evidence-based interventions in two studies (8,9)
- A Workplace Characteristics Questionnaire examined physical and organisational aspects of the work environment, in one study (21).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for demographic outcomes

Study (Author)	Year	Region	N	Sex (%)	Age	Years of Experience	Work Sector (%)	Work Shift (%)
Carmona-Barrientos et al.	2016	Cádiz	272	62.1 Female 37.9 Male	36.4 (6.6)	9.1 (4.4)	63.1 private, 22.1 public, 14.8 both	46.69 continuous 53.31 split
González-Sánchez et al.	2016	Extremadura	115	–	–	–	67.8 private, 20.9 public, 11.3 both	Not reported
Gisbert et al.	2008	Murcia & Valencia	261	63.6 Female 36.4 Male	34.7 (10.45)	–	41,4 private 58.4 public	Not reported
Rodríguez-Nogueira et al.	2022	Spain	472	69.7 Female 31.3 Male	33.4 (9.3)	7.7 (8.0)	73.9 private, 26.1 public	56.3 continuous 43.7 split
Rodríguez-Nogueira et al.	2024	Spain	471	68.4 Female 31.6 Male	33.3 (8.1)	10.7 (7.8)	73.9 private, 26.1 public	56.3 continuous 43.7 split
Rodríguez-Nogueira et al.	2021	Spain	472	68.4 Female 31.6 Male	33.3 (8.1)	10.7 (7.8)	73.9 private, 26.1 public	56.3 continuous 43.7 split
Grande-Alonso et al.	2023	Madrid	174	46 Female 54 Male	29.7 (6.17)	5.0 (3.7)	100 private	40,2 continuous 59.8 split

Values provided for age and years of experience: mean and standard deviation (SD). TR: Therapeutic Relationship; EBP: Evidence Based Practice

Burnout Levels

Across studies, Spanish physiotherapists exhibited moderate levels of EE and DP, with some variation according to employment type, sector, and experience. Early-career PTs tended to report higher EE and DP (21), while freelance professionals generally showed lower emotional exhaustion and higher PA (22). Overall, PA levels were moderate to high (6, 8, 9,16,19,20), except in certain contexts of contracted employment where perceived accomplishment was lower. These patterns suggest that structural and organisational factors, rather than individual characteristics alone, play a central role in burnout risk.

Table 3. Descriptive and comparative analysis of studies on the burnout syndrome index.

Study (Author)	MBI EE Subscale		MBI DP Subscale		MBI PA Subscale	
	Freelance	Contracted	Freelance	Contracted	Freelance	Contracted
Carmona-Barrientos et al.	21.64 (10.57)		6.57 (4.65)		39.52 (5.97)	
González-Sánchez et al.	20.02 (11.33)		7.45 (5.42)		37.77 (7.39)	
Sánchez-Gisbert et al.	21.39 (11.05)		5.74 (4.92)		38.65 (7.52)	
Rodríguez-Nogueira et al. (2022)	26.8 (10.4)		9.6 (4.2)		38.3 (5.1)	
Rodríguez-Nogueira et al. (2024)	26.9 (10.4)		9.7 (4.2)		38.2 (5.1)	
Rodríguez-Nogueira et al. (2021)	26.9 (10.3)		9.6 (4.1)		38.2 (5.1)	
Grande-Alonso et al.	Freelance 16 (16.85)	Contracted 33.5 (10.93)	Freelance 6 (5.00)	Contracted 13 (5.74)	Freelance 39.5 (6.67)	Contracted 31 (9.63)

Values are presented as mean and standard deviation (SD). EE: emotional exhaustion; DP: depersonalisation; PA: personal accomplishment.

Occupational and Relational Factors

High workload, time pressure, number of patients treated, and limited time per patient were consistently associated with increased EE and DP (22). Employment precarity and lower remuneration were also linked to elevated burnout scores, particularly among contracted PTs (22). Conversely, greater professional autonomy, flexible scheduling, and higher income, as observed among freelance physiotherapists, appeared to serve as protective factors.

The relational dimension of burnout was prominent: depersonalisation often involved emotional withdrawal from patients, which may reduce empathy and weaken therapeutic

relationships. This dynamic can diminish perceived personal accomplishment and reinforce emotional exhaustion, highlighting the importance of considering burnout as a relational and systemic phenomenon in physiotherapy practice.

Other Work-Related and Contextual Factors

Physical workload and occupational demands (including repetitive manual techniques, musculoskeletal strain, and long patient contact hours) contributed to early resource depletion (22), particularly among younger PTs. Organizational stressors such as inadequate staffing, limited professional development opportunities, and perceived job insecurity further exacerbated burnout risk. Evidence from complementary instruments reinforced these findings: higher perceived occupational stress, lower empathy or relational engagement, and weaker therapeutic alliance scores were associated with elevated EE and DP, and lower PA.

Summary of Patterns

Taken together, the studies indicate that burnout among Spanish physiotherapists is moderately prevalent, with consistent patterns linking higher burnout to early-career status, public sector employment, high patient load, limited consultation time, and job precarity. Protective factors include professional autonomy, flexible employment, higher income, and strong therapeutic alliances. Across instruments, burnout appears to be influenced by a combination of occupational, structural, and relational factors, rather than by individual vulnerabilities alone.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this review indicate that burnout among Spanish physiotherapists is strongly associated with occupational and structural characteristics of the profession rather than exclusively with individual vulnerability. When interpreted through the JD–R framework, burnout emerges from sustained imbalance between job demands—such as high patient load, time pressure, administrative burden and employment precarity—and insufficient job resources, including organisational support, professional autonomy and economic stability.

National workforce data provide important contextual support for this interpretation. According to the most recent data from the Spanish National Institute of Statistics (INE, 2022), 66,178 physiotherapists were registered and eligible to practice in Spain (23), of whom 62% were female and 38% male (24). Notably, 76% of registered physiotherapists were under the age of 45, with 43% below 35 years. When compared with other healthcare

professions, physiotherapy presents a markedly younger workforce profile, with only 53% of nurses and 39% of physicians under 45 years of age (25). The comparatively young profile of the Spanish physiotherapy workforce may be partially linked to the demanding nature of the profession. Limited access to continuous professional development (26), employment precarity and financial concerns may disproportionately affect early-career physiotherapists, accelerating resource depletion during the first years of practice .

This demographic distribution is consistent with the sociodemographic characteristics reported across the studies included in this review and may partially explain the higher vulnerability to burnout observed in early-career professionals. Younger physiotherapists often face lower salaries, reduced contractual stability and limited professional autonomy. From a Conservation of Resources perspective, these conditions may accelerate resource depletion during the first years of professional practice, increasing susceptibility to emotional exhaustion and depersonalisation.

Furthermore, the physical effort required physiotherapy is characterised by considerable physical demands, with documented high prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal disorders (27) and occupational pain (28). These physical stressors, combined with emotional labour and financial insecurity, may contribute to early professional attrition. Evidence suggesting that some physiotherapists leave the profession within the first seven years (29) aligns with Gisberts findings indicating higher burnout prevalence in early stages of professional development. The convergence between national workforce demographics and burnout patterns reinforces the interpretation of burnout as a structural occupational phenomenon rather than solely an individual vulnerability.

Considering occupational factors, the consistent association observed across studies between workload variables, particularly number of patients treated per day and time allocated per consultation, and higher EE and DP scores further supports the JD–R framework. Excessive job demands without adequate buffering resources may not only intensify exhaustion but also compromise therapeutic engagement. Job insecurity and lower pay in the private sector, were related to lower personal accomplishment (PA), while greater professional autonomy, flexible schedules, and higher income among freelance physiotherapists appeared protective.

The relational dimension of burnout is especially relevant in physiotherapy. Empathy, both cognitive and affective, was generally inversely related to DP and positively associated with PA, although findings from Rodriguez-Nogueira et al. suggest that insufficient coping strategies may link high empathy to increased EE and DP, potentially leading to compassion

fatigue. Given the centrality of therapeutic alliance in rehabilitation outcomes (9), depersonalisation may have dual consequences: diminishing professional well-being while simultaneously affecting treatment quality and adherence. This relational erosion may generate a negative feedback loop in which reduced empathy weakens therapeutic engagement, decreasing perceived treatment impact and progressively eroding personal accomplishment. Over time, this cycle may consolidate more persistent burnout profiles. However, the suggest that evidence based practice support stronger patient relationships and protect against burnout (19).

Higher depersonalisation scores observed in the public sector may reflect structural workload imbalances. In 2022, the ratio of physiotherapists within the Spanish public system was approximately one per 10,000 inhabitants, suggesting substantial service pressure (30). Although no universally established staffing benchmark exists for physiotherapists, comparisons with international rehabilitation workforce recommendations highlight potential resource constraints (17). Within a JD-R framework, insufficient staffing may intensify patient load and reduce consultation time, increasing emotional strain and distancing responses. In parallel, perceptions of job insecurity, lower remuneration relative to other public healthcare professionals and limited organisational support—identified in several included studies—may further compound depersonalisation risk (31). Conversely, findings indicating higher personal accomplishment among freelance physiotherapists suggest that greater income autonomy and work flexibility may function as protective resources, reinforcing the structural interpretation of burnout patterns across employment contexts.

Taken together, these findings suggest that burnout among Spanish physiotherapists reflects a complex interaction between demographic characteristics, employment structures, physical workload and relational demands. Addressing burnout therefore requires approaches that move beyond individual coping enhancement and consider organisational and systemic determinants.

Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting these findings. First, this review was conducted by a single reviewer. Although a comprehensive search strategy across multiple databases was implemented using both MeSH and thesaurus terms, the absence of independent dual screening introduces potential selection bias and may affect reproducibility. Also, although PRISMA guidelines were followed for reporting, the protocol was not prospectively registered. Future systematic reviews incorporating multiple reviewers and protocol registration would strengthen methodological rigour.

Second, all included studies employed cross-sectional quantitative designs, limiting causal inference and preventing longitudinal analysis of burnout trajectories. The absence of qualitative research represents a notable gap, as lived experiences, contextual determinants and coping mechanisms among Spanish physiotherapists remain underexplored. Integrating qualitative methodologies could provide deeper explanatory insight into the mechanisms underlying emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and reduced personal accomplishment.

Finally, heterogeneity in sample sizes, regional representation and measurement instruments may limit comparability across studies. Although most studies employed the MBI or MBI-HSS, differences in reporting formats and contextual variables constrain direct quantitative synthesis and precluded formal meta-analysis.

Implications for practice and policy

The findings of this review suggest that reducing burnout among Spanish physiotherapists requires multi-level strategies that extend beyond individual coping enhancement. Consistent with the JD–R framework, recalibrating the balance between occupational demands and available resources may represent a central preventive approach.

At the organisational level, moderating patient load and ensuring adequate time allocation per consultation may reduce sustained emotional strain while simultaneously strengthening the therapeutic alliance. Given the established relationship between therapeutic alliance and treatment adherence and outcomes, workload regulation may function both as a workforce protection mechanism and as a quality-of-care safeguard.

Educational institutions may contribute preventively by embedding structured training in stress management, reflective practice, perspective-taking and evidence-based clinical reasoning within undergraduate curricula. Early development of these competencies may enhance professional resources prior to repeated exposure to occupational stressors.

From a structural perspective, employment precarity and income disparities consistently appear associated with higher burnout scores. While causal relationships cannot be inferred from cross-sectional evidence, these findings align with broader occupational health literature identifying job insecurity and limited economic progression as chronic stressors. Policies aimed at enhancing employment stability, transparent career progression and equitable remuneration may therefore contribute to strengthening personal accomplishment and mitigating emotional exhaustion over time.

Collectively, these results reinforce the conceptualisation of burnout among physiotherapists as a systemic occupational phenomenon rather than solely an individual psychological condition. Addressing organisational and structural determinants may ultimately improve workforce sustainability while safeguarding patient care quality.

CONCLUSION

Burnout among Spanish physiotherapists is primarily associated with occupational stressors related to workload, job precarity and limited organisational support. These factors contribute to higher emotional exhaustion and depersonalisation and reduced personal accomplishment, particularly among contracted professionals. Addressing working conditions, promoting professional development and strengthening organisational support may reduce burnout risk and improve workforce retention.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. Burn-out an "occupational phenomenon": International Classification of Diseases. [Internet] 2019. [Cited 2025 March 10]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news/item/28-05-2019-burn-out-an-occupational-phenomenon-international-classification-of-diseases>
2. Melamed S, Shirom A, Toker S, Berliner S, Shapira I. Burnout and risk of cardiovascular disease: evidence, possible causal paths, and promising research directions. *Psychol Bull.* 2006 May;132(3):327-53.
3. Demerouti, E., Bakker, A. B., Nachreiner, F., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2001). The job demands–resources model of burnout. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 499–512.
4. Hobfoll, S. E. (1989). Conservation of resources: A new attempt at conceptualizing stress. *American Psychologist*, 44(3), 513–524.
5. Mikolajewska. E. Work-related stress and burnout in physiotherapists - A literature review. *Medycyna Pracy.* 2014; 65 (5).
6. González-Sánchez. B, González López-Arza. M.V, Montanero-Fernández. J, Varela-Donoso. E, Rodríguez-Mansilla. J, Mingote-Adán. J.C. Burnout syndrome prevalence in physiotherapists. *Rev Assoc Med Bras.* 2017 Apr; 63(4): 361-365.
7. De Diego-Cordero. R, Iglesias-Romo. M, Badanta. B, Lucchetti. G, Vega-Escaño. J; Burnout and spirituality among nurses: A scoping review. *Explore.* Sept-Oct 2022; 16 (5): 612-620.
8. Rodríguez-Nogueira Ó, Leirós-Rodríguez R, Pinto-Carral A, Álvarez-Álvarez MJ, Fernández-Martínez E, Moreno-Poyato AR. The relationship between burnout and empathy in physiotherapists: a cross-sectional study. *Ann Med.* 2022 Dec; 54(1):933-940.
9. Rodríguez-Nogueira Ó, Leirós-Rodríguez R, Pinto-Carral A, Álvarez-Álvarez MJ, Morera-Balaguer J, Moreno-Poyato AR. Relationship between competency for evidence-based practice and level of burnout of physical therapists with the establishment of the therapeutic relationship. *Physiother Theory Pract.* 2024 Feb;40(2):357-365.
10. Maslach C., Jackson S.E. Maslach Burnout Inventory. Manual. Consulting Psychologists Press; Palo Alto, CA, USA: 1981.
11. Feldt T, Rantanen J, Hyvönen K, Mäkikangas A, Huhtala M, Pihlajasaari P, Kinnunen U. The 9-item Bergen Burnout Inventory: factorial validity across organizations and measurements of longitudinal data. *Ind Health.* 2014;52(2):102-12.

12. Kristensen, T. S., Borritz, M., Villadsen, E., Christensen, K. B. The Copenhagen Burnout Inventory: A new tool for the assessment of burnout. *Work & Stress*. 2005; 19(3), 192–207.
13. Gil-Monte P.R., Figueiredo-Ferraz H. Psychometric properties of the ‘Spanish Burnout Inventory’ among employees working with people with intellectual disability. *Journal of Intellectual Disability Research*. 2012; 57 (10), 959-968.
14. Marcatto F, Di Blas L, Ornella L, Festa S, Ferrante D. The Perceived Occupational Stress Scale: A brief tool for measuring workers’ perceptions of stress at work. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*. 2022; 38(4), 293–306.
15. Melekhov, V., Medvedev, O. N., & Krägeloh, C. U. (2025). Interpersonal Reactivity Index (IRI). In O. N. Medvedev, C. U. Krägeloh, & R. J. Siegert (Eds.), *Handbook of assessment in mindfulness research* (pp. 1–13)
16. Burri S.D, Smyrk K.M, Melegy M.S, Hussein N.I, Tuttle B.D, Clewley D.J. Risk factors associated with physical therapist burnout: a systematic review. *Physiotherapy*. 2022 Sept; 116: 9-24.
17. Willard-Grace R, Knox M, Huang B, Hammer H, Kivlahan C, Grumbach K. Burnout and Health Care Workforce Turnover. *Ann Fam Med*. 2019 Jan;17(1):36-41.
18. Salyers MP, Bonfils KA, Luther L, Firmin RL, White DA, Adams EL, Rollins AL. The Relationship Between Professional Burnout and Quality and Safety in Healthcare: A Meta-Analysis. *J Gen Intern Med*. 2017 Apr;32(4):475-482.
19. Rodríguez-Nogueira Ó, Leirós-Rodríguez R, Pinto-Carral A, Álvarez-Álvarez MJ, Morera-Balaguer J, Moreno-Poyato AR. Examining the Association between Evidence-Based Practice and Burnout among Spanish Physical Therapists: A Cross-Sectional Study. *J Pers Med*. 2021 Aug 18;11(8):805.
20. Carmona-Barrientos I, Gala-León F.J, Lupiani-Giménez M, Cruz-Barrientos A, Lucena-Anton D, Moral-Munoz J.A. Occupational stress and burnout among physiotherapists: a cross-sectional survey in Cadiz (Spain). *Hum Resour Health*. 2020 Nov 25;18(1):91.
21. Serrano Gisbert M.F, de Los Fayos E.J, Hidalgo Montesinos M.D. Burnout en fisioterapeutas españoles [Burnout in Spanish physiotherapists]. *Psicothema*. 2008 Aug;20(3):361-8.
22. Grande-Alonso M, Castillo-Alcañiz B, Paraíso-Iglesias P, Cuenca-Martínez F, La Touche R, Vidal-Quevedo C. Comparative analysis of the burnout syndrome index between contract and freelance physiotherapists: An observational study. *Work*. 2023;76(3):1135-1144.

23. INE- Instituto Nacional de Estadística. Estadística de Profesionales Sanitarios Colegiados Año 2022. [Internet] May 2023. [Cited 2025 Sept 14]. Available from: https://www.ine.es/prensa/epsc_2022.pdf
24. INE- Instituto Nacional de Estadística. Distribución del nº de Fisioterapeutas por Comunidades y Ciudades autónomas de colegiación, edad y sexo. [Internet]. May 2024. [Cited 2025 Sept 14]. Available from: <https://datos.gob.es/es/catalogo/ea0010587-distribucion-del-n-de-fisioterapeutas-por-comunidades-y-ciudades-autonomas-de-colegiacion-edad-y-sexo-identificador-api-67346>
25. INE- Instituto Nacional de Estadística. Estadística de Profesionales Sanitarios Colegiados Año 2023. [Internet] May 2024. [Cited 2025 Sept 14]. Available from: <https://ine.es/dyngs/Prensa/es/EPSC2023.htm>
26. Skamagki G, Blackburn L, Biggs D, Kolitsida M, Black C, Shanmugam S. Exploring burnout, perfectionism, and moral injury among UK physiotherapists: A qualitative study on professional fulfilment and well-being. *PLoS ONE*. 2025 Feb;20(2).
27. Brattig B, Schablon A, Nienhaus A, Peters C. Occupational accident and disease claims, work-related stress and job satisfaction of physiotherapists. *J Occup Med Toxicol*. 2014 Dec 2;9(1):36.
28. Campo MA, Weiser S, Koenig KL. Job strain in physical therapists. *Phys Ther*. 2009 Sep;89(9):946-56.
29. Dickson C, de Zoete RM. High-level physical therapy and workforce attrition: A paradox? *Braz J Phys Ther*. 2022 Jul-Aug;26(4):100432.
30. World Health Organization. The need to scale up rehabilitation [Internet]. Geneva: World Health Organization. 2018 Jul [Cited 2025 Sep 14]. Available from: https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/documents/health-topics/rehabilitation/call-for-action/need-to-scale-up-rehab-july2018.pdf?sfvrsn=f627c34c_5
31. Alexias G, Papandreopoulou M, Togas C. Work Engagement and Burnout in a Private Healthcare Unit in Greece. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2024 Jan 25;21(2):130.